

**COPYRIGHT ABUSES IN NIGERIA HIGHER
INSTITUTION: CAUSES AND EFFECTS ON
INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY;**

(A CASE STUDY OF FEDERAL UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY MINNA AND NIGER
STATE COLLEGE OF EDUCATION MINNA)

BY

**MAKOSHI STEPHEN MIKAH
MAT NO: 2001/13378BI**

**DEPT. OF LIBRARY AND INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY
FEDERAL UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY, MINNA, NIGER
STATE.**

NOVEMBER, 2007.

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**A PROJECT PRESENTED TO THE DEPARTMENT OF LIBRARY
SCIENCE AND INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY IN THE SCHOOL OF
SCIENCE AND SCIENCE EDUCATION**

**FEDERAL UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY, MINNA, NIGER
STATE.**

**IN PARTIAL FULFILLMENT OF THE AWARD OF BACHELOR OF
TECHNOLOGY IN LIBRARY AND INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY.**

NOVEMBER, 2007.

CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that, this research project, which was signed and approved on behalf of the department by the under listed, was carried out by Makoshi Stephen Mikah with matriculation number 2001/13378bi. Is hereby submitted for assessment of the award of Bachelor of Technology, Degree(B.TECH) in the Department of Library and Information Technology, Federal University of Technology, Minna.

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Head of Department

Dr. E.C. Madu (Phd)

Date

External Examiner

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DECLARATION

I, **Makoshi Stephen Mikah** with the matriculation number 2001/13378BI hereby declare that this research project, “copyright Abuses In Nigerian Higher Institutions: Causes and Effects;Case Study Of Federal University Of Technology Minna and Niger State College of Education Minna is Carried out under the supervision of Miss Grace Aliu and presented in partial fulfillment of the award of Bachelor of Technology (B.Tech) Degree in Library and Information Technology has not been presented for any degree elsewhere, to the best of my knowledge

Makoshi Stephen Mikah

Date.

DEDICATION

I reverently dedicate this project to the ALMIGHTY GOD the owner of wisdom and understanding (omniscience), the entire Makoshi families, my friends, all those who has contributed to the success of my education, and lastly, to all the ghetto products. It is well, GOD bless you in JESUS name. AMEN

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My profound gratitude goes to the ALMIGHTY GOD who in his infinite love, mercy and grace has brought me thus far, to Him be the glory.

Big thanks to my loving and caring parents Mr and Mrs Mikah M Yashim for their spiritual, moral and financial support throughout my academic program. I Bless name the lord for giving me such parents. You shall live to eat the fruit of your labour. You are favoured.

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ABSTRACT

The high rate of copyright abuses in the country is a source of concern to every right thinking individual. "Knowledge" as we all know is power. The success of any nation depends greatly on the quality and quantity of the kind of information generated in that country. This information is transmitted and recorded in both printed and non-printed format through the tireless effort of people with creative mind who live amidst us. In Nigeria, the efforts of these originators of such vital tools are thrown down the drain due to the diverse infringement activities going on the country. This study has investigated the causes and effects of copyright abuses in F.U.T. Minna and Niger State C.O.E Minna. It is good to note that, this research is profitable for general public enlightenment on the concept of copyright and usage. Case study research design was adopted and the validated questionnaires were administered to students and staff of both schools. The returned questionnaires were analyzed and presented on simple percentages tabulation. From the result obtained, it was reveals that, 89.9% of the students and 100% of the staff are aware of copyright law while 10.6% has no idea. The factors that triggered copyright abuses includes: lack of knowledge about copyright, scarcity of some vital information material, availability of printing materials and equipment, lack of strong copyright system and cost of reproduction is cheaper than cost of origination. Those harmful practices that infringed on the right of the author includes; photocopying and piracy, distributing copyrighted work to the public for commercial purposes, renting and lending the work to the public for business purposes, making adaptation of the work in public and broadcasting the work over electronic media. The nation economy seemed stuck in limbo because of the adverse effects of these negative practices. If the following measures are strictly observed, this menace can be curtailed. These includes; educating the general public on copyright related issues, creating incentives for copyright stake-holders, establishment of strong copyright system, imposing higher penalties on different copyright abuses, copyright should be taught in the secondary and tertiary institution, license should be given to local publisher to foster constant supply of scarce information resources e.t.c. It is crystal clear to note that, Nigeria student and academic staff are aware of copyright law. However, more enlightenment programmes in schools, urban and rural areas should be given the top most priority. No doubt, the growth and development of any nation rely on the protection and promotion of this vital tool called information. Therefore, the need for a strong copyright system should be a collective responsibility.

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.0 BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

Information being a strong tool for national development and this is stored in both printed and non-printed media. These vital resources are needed by professionals of different human endeavour. Without it, they cannot function effectively and efficiently. This intellectual properties are available in diverse format. Wall (1993), describe intellectual property as copyright. These may include; original “literary” like literary work, tables, and computer programme (software) compilation e.t.c. or “artistic” such as photography’s, and artistic work. Copyright may also consist sound recording, films, broadcast or cable programmes, typographical arrangement of published edition or printed page whether text or illustrations.(Wall,1993)

All these information materials are created and disseminated on a daily basis through the tireless effort of people with creative mind within us. For these people to continue doing their good work, they need protection against any form of infringement. More so, they need support and encouragement from both government and the general public.

This is not so in Nigerian context. Many authors and other stakeholder in the copyright business have had their work being infringed in one way or the other. These people are prevented from reaping the fruit of their labour. How these people (i.e. stakeholder in the copyright business) can compete favourably with their counter part in other countries with the ongoing copyright infringement activities the country?

Ojiji (1985) respectfully state that, “virtually all Nigerian publishers are falling victims of piracy. Out of more than 30 publishing houses in the country, 50% of them had their titles pirated.

Ali (1987) attested that “book piracy” passes a great danger to both publishers and authors in the country.

Ade-Saoye (1992) also confirmed that book piracy is one of the greatest problem facing publishers. He added that, the bestselling titles are the target of pirate.

Igbengbu (1993) reveals that photocopying is a major threat to intellectual properties in Nigeria universities.

It is true that the Nigeria government has made law to arrest copyright abuses in the country, yet the impact is not felt. Most of the perpetrators saw copyright infringement as a good money venture, because the law is not taken it due course. Reason for this, could be as a result of poor implementation and enforcement of the law.

The focus of this study is to critically examine the root causes of copyright abuses, the ways through which copyright is violated, it negative effect and also make recommendation where necessary.

1.1 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The role of copyright violation in Nigerian higher institution is a source of concern to both the government and the general public. Why do Nigeria inhabitant chooses to violate the law? Are they violating it because of lack of knowledge or deliberately? What other is factor responsible for their action? These and many more issues shall be addressed in this study.

1.2 PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

This research is aiming at identifying the possible causes and effect of copyright abuses in Nigeria higher institutions as the affects intellectual property production in the country. After

thorough studying this said research, one should be able to achieve the following objectives.

He/she should be able to ascertain:

- i. Whether Nigeria law has provision for intellectual property right protection.
- ii. The level of copyright law awareness among Nigeria student.
- iii. The causes of copyright violation in the country.
- iv. The negative effect of copyright abuses to all intellectual property production and the economy.
- v. The possible ways this law is abused.
- vi. The appropriate measures to be taken to curtail this ugly situation.
- vii. To re-awaken the enforcement of this law by the government agencies saddled with the responsibility of ensuring law and order in the country.

1.3 RESEARCH QUESTIONS

This study specifically seeks to answer the following:

1. is there law that protect intellectual property right?
2. Do Nigeria populace are fully aware of the existence of such law?
3. Why do they choose to violate the law?
4. What are the causes of copyright abuses?
5. Identify the possible ways this law could be abused?
6. What effect does it have on intellectual property production and the economy?
7. Is there any remedy to this menace? Identify the suitable measures to be taken to arrest this ugly situation?
8. Does the government have any role to play to this effect?

1.4 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

This study is profitable for general public enlightenment about the concept and usage of copyright product. It is necessary to specify that the findings of this research if directly apply, will help government agencies such as Nigeria copyright commission and other law enforcement agencies on the need for a strong copyright system, and this will discourage piracy.

1.5 SCOPE OF THE STUDY

To achieve the objectives of this study, the researcher has to device a way of conducting this research with ease. To make the work stress free, the researcher is limiting the scope of this study to federal university of technology and Niger State College of Education, Minna. With the assumption that similar problem occur in other state of the federation.

This study seeks to examine the cause and effect of copyright abuses in Nigeria higher institution. It also seeks to identify the possible ways through which this law is violated, and it negative effects on copyright production and the economy.

1.6 LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

Other higher institution like federal polytechnic Bida, Niger State Polytechnic Zungeru, and Federal College of Education Kontagora where supposed to be included in this research but are not due to time factor and distance.

Limited sample of data were used and access to accurate number of students and staff of both institution were not readily available for this research.

Lastly, some information materials and finance are other drawback to this research.

1.7 DEFINITION OF TERMS

Abuse: Unfair, cruel or violent treatment of copyright

Copyright: See also as intellectual property

Copyright Law: An exclusive legal right that protect author's intellectual properties against any form of violation.

Intellectual Property/ Intellectual Product: Original product of the mind put in a tangible format, such as written word or other forms of expression such material could include. Literary work artistic work, photographs, software, video tape, cable program etc.

Moral Right: Right to claim authorship of copyright.

Reserved Right: An exclusive legal right given to author to control the production and reproduction of copyright. Anybody, who want to use the said product, must seek for the author's permission. Otherwise that person has committed copyright theft.

Work: See also an intellectual property.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.0 INTRODUCTION

The term copyright is not a recent phenomenon. It has being in existence for decades. The background details of this research is provided in this chapter with the hope that, many people will be better enlighten about the concept of the subject matter.

2.1 THE CONCEPT OF COPYRIGHT

According to Encyclopedia Americana (1983) define copyright as the exclusive right that protect an author composer, or artist from having his work recorded, performed, displayed, translated, distributed or reproduced by way of copies, phonorecords, or other version (derivative works) “Except with his permission, subject to specified limitation. The intellectual property right comes into existence automatically from the very day the original work is produce it become legible for legal protection”.

Oxford Advance Dictionary (2000) also explained that if a person or an organization holds the copyright on a piece of writing, music etc they are the only people who have the legal right to publish, broadcast, perform it e,t.c, any other people must ask for their permission to use it or any part of it: copyright expire 70 years after the death of the author.

Harrod’s Librarian’s glossary and reference book (1990) define copyright as, “A procedure whereby the originator of a piece of intellectual property (book, article, piece of music etc) receives due recompense for the inventiveness or imagination expended.

Kent (1972) defines copyright as “The right generally secured by law to author of literary, dramatic, musical and artistic work to authorize the production or reproduction of such work”.

Copyright according to Ike (1992) “Is the right granted to an individual against unauthorized copyright or reproduction of his intellectual creature or work.

From the above definitions, it is glaring that copyright is all about the protection of author’s intellectual property right from unauthorized production or reproduction of such work.

Copyright is not designed to limit public access to information, but to ensure that economic and moral rights of the authors are protected. Copyright law is based on the assumption that an author is more likely be motivated to embark on continuous production of intellectual products (Unpublished 2006 Lit 415 Note).

Copyright however, does not only protect author’s intellectual properties, it also recognizes the right of publishers/distributors, the consumers and the society at large (Harrod’s Librarian Glossary and reference book 1990).

2.2 **COPYRIGHT IS “INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY”**

According Wall (1993) the term intellectual property was first coined to cover literary, dramatic, musical and artistic work; design of articles or devices; and inventions. He further describes a person who creates and record an original product of the mind to be the “prime owner” of the “intellectual property”.

Why say “prime owner”?

Intellectual property can change hand (transfer of ownership) by assignment. Whether wholly or partially. An author normally assign a publisher the right to reproduce copies of his or her work in return for payment usually refer to as “royalty” which is a percentage of the sale price of the publish work.

Why say the term “intellectual property was first coined”?

Because nowadays-copyright law give right of protection not only to originators but also to those who create physical format for original distribution or sales such as publishers, producer of audio visual media and provider of particular public services such as broadcasting and electronic database, right are given to performer too. (Wall 1993)

2.3 **KINDS OF COPYRIGHT WORK**

Wall (1993) stated that copyright subsists in the following:

- a. Original Literacy, dramatic, musical or artistic works. (Compilation, tables and computer programmes are defined as “literary”; photograph are “artistic” irrespective of the nature)
- b. Sound recording, films, broadcast or cable programmes “films” includes video recording or any moving image, while “cable programme” includes not only cable TV but also public accessible online electronic database or radio information service.
- c. The typographic arrangement of a published edition of printed pages. Whether text or music or illustration etc.

2.4 **OWNERSHIP OF COPYRIGHT**

Naturally, copyright of any work or publication belong to the author, section 9 of the copyright Act (the laws the federation of Nigeria 1990 chapter 68) shade more light as follows:

1. Copyright conferred by sections 2 and 3 of this Act, shall vest initially in the author.
2. Notwithstanding subsection (6) of section 10 of this Act where a work -
 - i. Is commissioned by a person who is not the author’s employer under a contract of service or apprenticeship; or

- ii Not having been so commissioned is made in the course of the author's employment; copyright shall be vested to the author unless otherwise stated in writing under the contract.
3. Where any intellectual product is made by the author in the course of his employment by the proprietor of newspaper, magazine or similar periodical under a contract of service or apprenticeship. The proprietor shall be the owner of the copyright provided there is absence of any agreement to the contrary.
4. In the case of cinematograph film or sound recording, the author shall be obliged to conclude, prior to the making of the work, contract in writing with all those whose works are to be used in the making of the work.
5. Copyright conferred by section 4 of this Act, shall vest initially in the Government on behalf of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, in the state authority on behalf of the state in question, or in the international body in question, as the case may be, and not in the author

2.5 **AUTHOR'S RESERVED RIGHT**

According to Flint (1997) authors are given legal right to control the doing of the following:

- a. copying the work;
- b. issuing copies of the work to the public;
- c. renting or lending copies of the work to the public;
- d. performing, showing or playing the work in public;
- e. broadcasting the work or including it in a cable programme service;
- f. Making an adaptation of the work or doing any of the above acts in relation to an adoption.

The above-mentioned acts are restricted to the author alone. This is also refer to as author's reserved rights without a written permission from the owner, that person has infringe on the right of the copyright owner. This Act is punishable in both criminal and civil court. (Unpublished document – 2006 Lit 415 Note).

.6 **FAIR USE**

The concept of copyright does not only protect author alone, it also protect potential user access to information. This is provided in the doctrine of fair use. The doctrine of fair use is the most important element, which strikes a balance between the just reward given to author and users accessibility to information.

Fair use is the acts that permit the reproduction of few pages from a copyrighted work such that it will not affect copyright owner access to their economic benefits. (Encyclopedia of Library and Information Science).

2.7 **MORE FACTS ABOUT COPYRIGHT**

Copyright does not protect idea until it is put in a tangible format such as written word or other forms of expression before it can gain protection. (Unpublished Material – 2006 Lit 415 Note).

Excluding authors, other stakeholder in the copyright business have limitation to the right given to them. For instance, a publishing house might be giving the right to reproduce a work by publishing it. But might not be given the right to distribute it to the public for commercial purpose or perform the work in the public by way of staging a theatre performance. Separate firms might be contracted for both the distribution and sells of the intellectual product. (Unpublished Document – 2006 Lit 415 note).

Copyright has duration for example; copyright may 70 years after the death of the known author. While for organization, copyright can only last 70 years after it was first published. (Wall, 1993). Copyright like other properties, could be transfer from person to person. (Transfer of ownership) through the following:

- i. By Assignment, this is usually done in writing
- ii. By licensing, also in writing
- iii. By testamentary disposition. The owner can write a “will” transferring ownership to another person (Unpublished document – 2006 Lit 415 note).

2.8 ORIGIN AND DEVELOPMENT OF COPYRIGHT

Copyright is not a recent innovation; it has its origin way back in time. According to Wall (1993) initially the term copyright was not formally used. It was literally used as “right to copy”.

Wall (1993) state that in the ancient time, what was said is all that matter not who say it. The growth of individualism was believed to date from about 6th Century BC in Classical Greece. Signing work of art and poem is the commonest feature. The right to make copies evolved in various societies as a means of controlling the flow of information.

Ancient China and Egypt are some of the examples of the extreme control of information flow compare with community property approach in Bali. Ancient Jewish law involved economic return for authors and their heir. In Rome, contracts were drawn up between authors and publishers (scribes) and both benefited. In the middle age, scribes in monasteries held virtual monopoly of production of copies.

In 1436 Gutenberg (German) invented printed with movable types. That leads to the exploitation of massive printed materials then.

In 1476 Caxton also introduced printing in England this led to the piracy activities within the country. The Stationers' Company in 1557, such as printer, book activities. Copyright was vested to publisher not until when the royal charter was expired on 1694, that piracy became rampant.

In 1709 the act of Queen Anne became the first "modern" copyright Law that protect printed work against piracy. This mark the beginning of copyright revolution worldwide.

The house of Lord decision in 1774 changed copyright ownership from publisher to author's right.

In 1886 Berne Convention declare author right in 3 principles:

- i. Foreign works should protect each member state in same manner as its own works.
- ii. Content, scope, duration of any work must not be below standard that was provided in the convention.
- iii. Automatic protection without registration or notice.

In 1952 universal copyright convention has compromised to Unity Berne Union with American system.

In 1956 copyright Act, soon overtaken by technology.

In 1988 copyright designs and patent Act.

Modern copyright law has evolved from balancing the needs of users for access to and exchange of information with the right of author and publisher to financial benefit. (Wall 1993).

2.9 COPYRIGHT AND THE CHANGING WORLD

The changing world and multiplicity of items led to substantial changes in copyright legislation and international agreement.

The universal declaration of human right (Article 27,2) states that “Everyone has the right to protection of the moral and material interest resulting from any scientific, literary or artistic production of which he is the author”.

Current technological advancement (databases, video-recordings) have put copyright law under stress. How can copyright legislators adhere to the above declaration when technological advancements are evolving daily? This remains one of the greatest challenges facing copyright legislation and international agreements.

In view of this, copyright legislation has to recognize the interest of the following:

- i. The creators of intellectual properties
- ii. The publisher/distribution
- iii. The consumers and
- iv. The society at large.

(Harrod’s Librarian’s Glossary and reference book 1990).

2.10 NATURE OF COPYRIGHT

According to Wall (1993) copyright is concerned with original work and any forms in which they may be published or released or perform for others. Copyright centred on the right to copy or to authorize copying by others. An author is not compelled to permit a publisher to make copies and sell them but, if permission is given, the author is entitled to benefit according to the agreement made in a contract with the publisher. Author’s right must be protected from copying or publication without permission especially in a way which could damage its market.

2.11 IMPORTANCE OF COPYRIGHT

- a. Incentive and economic benefit to the authors, publishers and other stake holders in the copyright business is guaranteed
- b. Copyright law tries to balance authors' right and users allowing them to gain from work and later make good the society.
- c. Copyright do not only protect originators and publishers from potential loss of earning, but it also encourage all concerned to create and published further works.

2.12 COPY ACT

The law of the federation of Nigeria"1900"chapter 68 has provisions for the protection of all stake holders in the copyright community.

The law stated that,

“an act make provision for the definition, protection, transfer, infringement of and remedy of penalty thereof of works, cinematograph film, sound recording, broadcast and other ancillary matter. ”(19th December,1988).

Work eligible for copyright are:

- 1(1) Subject to this section, the following shall be eligible for copyright
 - a. Literature work;
 - b. Artistic work
 - c. Musical
 - d. Cinematograph films
 - e. Sound recordings and
 - f. Broadcasts

- 1(2) A literary, musical or artistic a work shall not be eligible for copyright unless-
- a. sufficient effort has been expended on making the work to give it an original character;
 - b. The work has been fixed in any definite medium of expression now know or later to be developed, from which it can be perceived, reproduced, or otherwise communicated, either directly or with the aid of any machine or device.
- 1(3) An artistic work shall not be eligible for copyright, if at the time when the work is made, it is intended by the author to be used as model or pattern to be multiplied by any industrial process.
- 1(4) A work shall not be ineligible for copyright by reason only that the making of the work or the doing of any act in relation to the work involved an infringement of copyright in some other work.

Copyright by virtue of nationality or domicile. First schedule

2(1) Copyright shall be conferred by this section on every work eligible for copy right of which the author or, in the case of a work of joint authorship, any of the authors is to say

- (a) An individual who is a citizen of, or I Domiciled in Nigeria; or
- (b) A body corporate incorporated by or is under the laws of Nigeria

2(2) The term of copyright conferred by this section shall be calculated according to the table set out in the first schedule to this act..

2(3) In the case of anonymous or pseudonymous literary, musical or artistic work the copyright there in shall subsist until the end of the expiration of seventy years from the end of the year in which the work was first published.

Provided that, when the author becomes known, the term of copyright shall be calculated in accordance with paragraph 1 of the first schedule to this act.

2(4) In the case of a work of a work of joint authorship, a reference in the first schedule to this act to the death of the author shall be taken to refer to the author who dies last, whether or not he is a qualified person within subsection (1) of this Section.

Copyright by reference to country of origin

3(1) Copyright shall not be conferred by this section on every work other than a broadcast, which is eligible for copyright and which –

- a. Being a literary ,musical or artice work or a cinematograph film, is first published in Nigeria ;or
- b. Being a sound recording, is made in Nigeria, and which has not been the subjected of copyright conferred by section of this act.

3(2) Copyright conferred on a work by this section shall have the same duration as is provided by section 2 of this act in relation to the same type of work.

Copyright in works of government, state authority and international bodies. First schedule

4(1) Copyright shall be conferred by this section on every work eligible for copyright that is created by or under the direction or control of the government, a state authority, or a prescribed international body.

4(2) The term of copyright conferred by this section shall be calculated in accordance with the table set out in the first schedule to this section

General nature of copyrights. Second schedule

5(1) Subject to the exceptions specified in the second schedule to this act, copyright in a work shall be the exclusive right to control the doing in Nigeria of any of the following act that is –

- a. In the case of literary or musical, to do any or authorize the doing of any of the following act –
- i. reproduced the work in any material form;
 - ii. published the work;
 - iii. perform, the work;
 - iv. distribute to the public for commercial purpose, copies of the work, by way of rental, lease, hire, loan or similar; arrangement;
 - v. Make a cinematograph film or record in respect of the work produce, reproduced, perform or publish any translation of the work.
 - vi. Broadcast or communicate the work to the public by a loud speaker or any other similar device;
 - vii.
 - viii. Make any adaptation of the work;
 - ix. Do in relation to a translation or an adaptation of the work, and any of the act specify in relation to the work in subparagraph (i) - (vii) of this paragraph

b. In the case of an artistic work, to do or authorize the doing of any of the following act that is -

- i. reproduced the work in any material form;
- ii. Publish the work;
- iii. include the work in any cinematograph film
- iv. make any adaptation of the work;
- v. do in relation to an adaptation of the work any of the act specified in relation to the work in sub paragraph (i) to (iii) of this paragraph.

c. in the case of cinematograph film, to do or authorize the doing of any following act -

- i. a copy of the film:
- ii. cause the film, in so far as it consist of visual image to seeing in a public, and in so far sound to be heard in public
- iii. Make any record in embodying the recording in any parts of the sound track, associated with the film by utilizing such sound tracks.
- iv. Distribute to the public for commercial purpose copies of the work by way of rentals, lease, hire, loan or similar arrangement.

2. The doing of any of the act referred to in subsection (1) of this section shall be in respect of the whole or a substantial part of the work either in its original form or in any form recognizably derived from the original.

3. Copyright in a work of architecture shall also include the exclusive right to control the erection of any building that reproduces the whole or a substantial part of the work, either in its original form or in any recognizably derived form. However, this does not include the right to control the reconstruction of a building in the same style as the original to which the copyright relates.

2.13 COPY RIGHT ABUSES

Many researches has been conducted around the world to attest to the fact that copyright is violated throughout the world (advance country inclusive)

Book piracy has being the great threat to most publishers and authors in UK .this was confirmed by Veliotes (1988) president of AAP in his letter.

“Our member must not only suffer theft of intellectual properties abroad....but must endure the indignity of having pirated copies thrown back to their faces across national boundaries”.(Veliotes, 1988)

Table below reveals the effects of book piracy on publisher in UK: the chief offending nations 1992.

Table 2.1: Book Piracy

Countries	≤Million	Total (%)
China	45	22.5
Russia	20	10.0
Indonesia	15	7.5
India	11	5.5
Iran	10	5.0
Pakistan	9	4.5
Egypt	7	3.5
Turkey	6	3.0
Korea	6	3.0
Poland	5	2.5
Others	66	33.0
Total	200	100

Software piracy is a common phenomenon among the nations of the world. Rosenberg (1990) reaffirms that in his statement.

“I would like to leave you with the impression that if you make a single illegal copy of our software, you will spend the next five years in court, the following 10 in prison and forever your soul will suffer eternal damnation”.

The table below shows how software copyright is misused worldwide: revenue and percentage market share 1992.

Table 2.2: Software Piracy

Country	% falling to piracy	US & losses (Million)
Australia/New Zealand	45	160
Benelux	66	419
France	73	1200
Germany	62	1000
Italy	86	550
Japan	92	3000
Korea	82	648
Singapore	41	24
Spain	86	362
Sweden	60	171
Taiwan*	93	585
Thailand	99	181
UK	54	685
United State	35	1900

Source: BSA 1993

Taiwan* figure reflects losses to US software publishers only (Gurnsey 1995)

2.14 COPYRIGHT ABUSES IN NIGERIA

The followings are facts that prove that copyright is also violated in Nigeria. Piracy has been and will always be the major ways through which copyright is being violated. There are various forms of piracy activities going on in the country. Nothing that is reproducible is spared.

Starting from audio cassette, video tapes, CDS, computer programme (software) and all paper based printed materials are not left out.

Igbengbu (1993) reveals that photocopying is the commonest medium most book based intellectual products are violated in Nigerian Universities, he unveiled that there are 173 photocopying centres in selected number of Nigerian Universities as follows:

Table 2.3: Photocopying in some Nigerian Universities

Institutions	Photocopying Centres
University of Benin	24
University of Ibadan	32
University of Ilorin	21
University of Lagos	20
University of Nsukka	22
University of Ile – Ife (OAU)	24
University of Port – harcourt	30
Total	173

(Unpublished document – 2006 LIT 415 note)

Ojiji (1985) the president of Nigerian Publisher Association in 1985/86 and 1987/88 stated that “virtually all Nigerian publisher are victims of piracy. He pointed out that, out of more than 30 publishing companies in the country, about 50% have had one or more of their title pirated. While about 20% of the annual turnover is lost to pirate by affected publishing houses.

Ade – saoye (1992) described book piracy as one of the greatest problem facing publishers. He noted that, most bestselling titles are the targets of pirate. Who send the copies to far eastern countries where identical copies are reproduce and transfer back to Nigeria for sale at a very low price.

Ali (1987) also conferment that “Book Piracy possess a great danger to both publisher and the author. Those damages includes the loss of revenue to government because the pirate do not

pay tax to it, yet on the other hand their activities seriously erode on the margin of bona fide publishing companies.”

2.15 CAUSES OF COPYRIGHT VIOLATION

Book scarcity is one of the causes of book piracy according to Higo (1989) observation. “The book crisis goes deeper and manifest itself in many form, some from more serious than others ... crisis of authorship, crisis availability, crisis of under publishing, crisis of distribution and crisis of librarian.

The World Bank Nigerian book sector study summary report states that financial constraints another factor the catalyzed book scarcity in the country. Due to the economic problem facing the country, little funding is allocated to book, in most Nigeria educational institutions.

A side from the above mentioned causes others causes might include

- i. Availability of reproduction material the presence of printing material like paper and other non-book material such as CDS, cassettes e.t.c are some of the factors that promote privacy
- ii. Advancement in technology and reprography over 2 decade has also made photocopying and computer system is a good facilitator of copyright theft.
- iii. Cost of origination exceeds cost or reproduction. It has been noticed and proved that the cost of origination of any intellectual work or product exceed that of the reproduction pirate do not undertake any of origination cost.
- iv. Legal protection lack force. Some legal generally see them as a mere cost of doing business (Apotiade 2004)

2.16 REMEDY TO THE PROBLEM

Apotiade (2004) listed out measures to be taken to out rest the menace as follows:

1. Incentive should be given to author and publisher through strong enforcement mechanism in place.
2. Intellectual properties must be treated reverently as an extension of the personality of the author as his or her child.
3. Strong copyright system discourages investment in piracy. Therefore, the police should destroy impound or sell the equipment used by copyright infringes.

4. There should be licensing option to reprint intellectual product. Copyright owners from foreign countries need to issue out licensees for production of their copyright locally. This will control scarcity of the product.
5. Copyright commission should set up collection societies to administer the collection and distribution of royalties due from photocopying on large scales,

1.17 **BENEFIT DERIVED FROM COPYRIGHT LAW**

- i. It encourages investment by enabling authors to be committed to the creation of manuscript thereby making a living for themselves and helping in the educational development of Nigerian populace.
- ii. People are encouraged to invest in intellectual properties productions.
- iii. Government will be paid adequate taxies from sales of unprinted product.
- iv. People will gain employment. (Apotiade 2004).

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

3.0 INTRODUCTION

This chapter contains the report of the method and procedure adopted in selecting the subject for research development, administration of data collection instrument and data analysis.

3.1 RESEARCH DESIGN

Case study research design was adopted in this research case study is an example of descriptive research method which concentrate on a single case or limited number of cases studied in-depth (Ekeh 2003).

Reason for adopting case study is to permits an in-depth s study of a given problem. Another reason is, case study is cheaper because data collection is less expensive than in the situation where large samples are involved.

3.2 POPULATION OF THE STUDY

The targeted populations for this study were drawn from the entire population of students and academic staff of FUT Minna and Niger State College of Education C.O.E Minna. These are represented in the table below.

Table3.1: Population Size

Respondent	F.U.T Minna	C.O.E Minna
Academic staff population	504	387
Students population	13, 000	6846

Source: FUT Minna 2007 student handbook, office of the Academic secretary and deputy registrar establishment C.O.E Minna. 2006 / 2007 Academic session.

Total number of academic staff of the two schools, $504 + 387 = 891$

Total numbers of the students of FUT Minna and C.O.E Minna is $13,000 + 6846 = 19,846$

3.3 **SAMPLE AND SAMPLING TECHNIQUE**

Sample is a sub-set of the population selected for purpose of investigation (Ekeh 2003). The sample will be drawn from large group of people which will provide information about the entire group.

Random sampling technique shall be employed. Reason for this is simple random sampling taken from a given population allowed equal and independent chances can easily visualize exactly what the research did.

3.4 **DETERMINING THE SAMPLE SIZE FROM THE GIVEN POPULATION**

Base on the recommended table for determining sample size from a given population as presented by Krejcie and Morgan (1970). The sample size for this research is given below.

Total staff (Academic staff) and student of F.U.T Minna and C.O.E Minna are $891 + 19,846 = 20,737$.

Therefore the sample size as presented by Morgan and Krejcie (1970) table is 377. the ratio of academic staff to student I given as 900 (Approximately) to 21,000 (Approximately) i.e.

$$\frac{900}{21000} = \frac{9}{210}$$

Therefore the proposed questionnaires to be administered staff and student of both higher institutions shall be 16 and 361 respectively.

3.5 INSTRUMENT OF DATA COLLECTION

The data collection instrument used for this research is questionnaires. Questionnaire is a series of items made up of question and statement which relate to the topic of a study and to which people are expected to respond by providing answer to those questions (Ekeh 2003).

Closed ended questionnaire shall be administered to provide short and precise statement for collection of data from the samples that represent the group of people. Closed ended questionnaire is easy to complete, it takes little time to fill, it keep respondent to the topic and is easy to tabulate and analyzed.

The questionnaire consist the following section.

- i. section A supply personal information of the respondent
- ii. Section B supply information of the subject matter
- iii. Section C provides information on the remedy to the problem.

3.6 VALIDITY OF THE INSTRUMENT

The questionnaires were drawn based on the objectives of the study. The questions were given to the supervisor and other experts for correction and approval.

3.7 METHOD OF DATA ANALYSIS AND REPRESENTATION

Data collection from the distributed closed ended questionnaire were organized, analyzed and presented using simple percentage and tabular representation.

CHAPTER FOUR

ANALYSIS, INTERPRETATION AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

4.0 INTRODUCTION

Data obtained from the designed questionnaires are presented in a simple tabulation and percentages base on the information provided by the respondents.

4.1 RESPONDENT RATE

The tables below shade more light on how the questionnaires were administered and collected from FUT Minna and Niger State C.O.E Minna. 377 questionnaires were supposed to be administered but due to financial constraint only 121 questionnaires were distributed. The table below shade more light.

Table 4.1: Respondent Rate

Respondent	No. of questionnaires distributed	No. of questionnaires collected	Percentage (%)
Students	105	94	89.5
Staff	16	13	81.3
Total	121	107	88.4

From the table above, out of 121 questionnaires that were issued out, 107 were returned given 88.40% response of the targeted population.

You could also see from the table above that, the total number of students and staff who took part in the sampling. 94 and 13 questionnaires were administered to both student and staff respectively.

Table 4.2: Age Group of the Respondents

The respondents were asked to indicate their age group.

Age group	16-20 %	21-25 %	26-30 %	30-35 %	36 and above %	Total %
Student	4 4.3	52 55.3	28 29.8	6 6.3	4 4.3	94 100
Staff	- 0	- 0	1 7.7	4 30.8	8 61.5	13 100

From the table above, 21 – 25 age groups with the total respondent of 52 / 55.3% are students which have the highest number of questionnaire administered in the student category follow by student with 26 – 30 age group which has 2.8 / 29.8%. Student with 16 – 20 and 36 years and above age group has the lowest number of questionnaire.

In the academic staff category, staff with 36 year and above age group has the highest questionnaires that were administered follow by staff with 31 – 35 age group, staff with 26 -30 age group is the lowest.

From the distribution above, it can be seen that majority of the two institution are between the age groups of 21 – 25 and 36 years and above respectively.

The respondent were asked if they have heard about copyright law before

Table 4.3: Copyright Awareness

Answer	Frequency			
	Student	%	Staff	%
Yes	84	89.4	13	100
No	8	8.5	-	0
Not sure	2	2.1	-	0
Total	94	100	13	100

The table above reveals that 84 / 89.4% of the students are informed about copyright law. 8 / 8.5% and 2 / 2.1% of the student are not informed.

The table above also reveals that 13 /100% of this staff are well informed. This could be as a result of the nature of their job.

Respondents were asked how they react to information material that they can hardly find in the market.

Table 4.4: Negative Practice on copyrighted work

Answer	Frequency			
	Student	%	Staff	%
Photocopy the whole copy	62	66.0	11	84.6
Duplicate the whole copy	22	23.4	2	15.4
Undecided	10	10.6	-	0
Total	94	100	13	100

The above table shows that photocopying the whole copy of scarce information material has the highest frequency.

62 or 66% of student and 11 or 84.6% of staff both attest to the fact that photocopying is the commonest way they can acquire scarce material. While 22 or 23.4% student and 2 or 15.4% staff also admitted that duplicating musical video and software is one of the ways they can secure scarce information material for their personal use.

Respondent were asked if they were fully aware of their action toward the scarce information resources is copyright violation and this is how they reacted

Table 4.5: Level of Copyright Awareness

Answer	Frequency			
	Student	%	Staff	%
Yes	50	53.2	13	100
No	26	27.7	-	0
Not sure	18	19.1	-	0
Total	94	100	13	100

The table above reveals that 50 or 53.2% of the students admitted that their action toward copyright product is copyright violation. 26 or 27.7% of them do not admit, while 18 or 19.1% of the student are not sure. This is a clear indication that they are aware of copyright law yet they don't know much about copyright violation.

13 or 100% of the staff were well informed this is a clear indication that the staff are well educated about copyright. This could be attributed as a result of the nature of their job.

The respondents were asked why do they violated the law, this is how they reacted

Table 4.6: Reasons for Copyright Violation

Answer	Students			Staff		
	Agree %	Disagree %	No idea %	Agree %	Disagree %	No idea %
I lack knowledge about copyright law	41 43.6	30 31.9	23 24.5	0 0	13 100	0 0
Scarcity of some information materials	70 74.5	9 9.6	15 15.9	13 100	0	0 0
It is a good business because one can make money within a short time	38 40.4	35 37.2	21 22.4	5 38.5	8 61.5	0 0
It is fun to violate it	19 20.2	48 51.1	27 28.7	0 0	13 100	0 0

From the table above, it can be seen that 41 or 43.6% of the student confirmed that they lack knowledge about copyright law. On the contrary the 100% of staff disagree. 70 Or 74.5% of the student reveals that scarcity of some information materials is a factor that catalyzes copyright

violation. 13 or 100% of the staff also attest to that fact. 38 or 40.4 of the student see copyright violation as money making venture while 35 or 37.2% of them disagree. 8 or 61.5% of the staff also disagree with the idea that copyright violation is a good business while 5 or 38.5% have a different view.

Respondents were asked to identify other factors that might be responsible for copyright abuses in the country.

Table 4.7: Factors that Influence Copyright Violation

Answer	Frequency					
	Students			Staff		
	Agree %	Disagree %	No idea %	Agree %	Disagree %	No idea %
Availability of printing materials	68 72.3	7 7.5	19 20.2	8 61.6	3 23.4	2 15.3
Availability of Hi-tech printing equipment	71 75.5	13 13.8	10 10.7	9 69.2	3 23.1	1 7.7
Lack of strong copyright system	47 50.0	21 22.4	26 27.7	10 76.9	1 7.7	2 15.3
Cost of reproduction is cheaper than cost of origination	66 70.2	15 16.0	13 13.8	13 100	0 0	0 0

The table above reveals that 68 or 72.3% of the students stick to the fact that availability of printing materials is one of the factor that facilitate copyright abuses. 8 or 61.6% also of the staff confirmed that.

71 or 75.5% of the student identify the availability of Hi-tech printing equipment as another factor. 9 or 69.2% of the staff also supported that motion. 47 or 50.0% of the students' belief that lack of strong copyright system is another factor. 10 or 76.9% of the staff also confirmed that.

Lastly 66 or 70.2% of the students ascertain that cost of reproduction of copyright is cheaper than cost of origination; this was also confirmed by the staff. 13 or 100% of them adhere to that.

Respondents were asked whether they believe that, copyright abuses have an adverse effect on the nation economy and intellectual property development. This is their reaction.

Table 4.8: Effect of Copyright Abuses on the Economy

Answer	Students	%	Staff	%
Agree	81	86.3	13	100
Disagree	3	3.2	0	0
No idea	10	10.6	0	0
Total	94	100	13	100

The table above reveals that 81 or 86.2% of the student believe that copyright abuse has a negative effect on the country economy progress. 10 or 10.6% of them have no idea while 3 or 3.2% disagree.

13 or 100% of the staff holds on to that fact that copyright violation has a devastating effect on the nation economy. This is because the staff are better informed on what it takes to create a product of the mind.

The respondents were asked to identify ways through which copyright law is violated.

Table 4.9: Ways of Copyright Violation

Answer	Students						Staff					
	Agree	%	Disagree	%	No idea	%	Agree	%	Disagree	%	No idea	%
Photocopying and piracy	85	90.4	5	5.3	4	4.3	12	92.3	1	7.7	0	0
Issuing copies to the public for commercial purposes	53	56.4	23	24.5	18	19.1	10	76.9	2	15.4	1	7.7
Renting and lending to the public	51	54.3	22	23.4	21	22.3	9	69.2	3	23.1	1	7.7
Performing, showing or playing the work in public	47	50.0	25	26.6	22	23.4	10	76.9	3	23.1	0	0
Making an adaptation of the work	43	45.7	21	22.3	30	32.0	9	69.2	4	30.8	0	0
Broadcasting the work over electronic media	44	46.8	30	32.0	20	21.3	8	61.5	4	30.8	1	7.7

From the table above we can see that 85 or 90.4% of the student agreed that photocopying and piracy are the major contributors to copyright violation. This was also approved by the opinions of the academic staff. 12 or 92.3% of them testify in favour to that.

We can also see from the table that 53 or 56.4% of the student admitted that issuing copies to the public is another medium. This was also support by 10 or 76.9% of the academic staff of both schools.

Renting and lending to the public for business purposes is also included. 51 or 54.3% of the student attested to that. 9 or 69.2% of the staff also adhered to that.

In the table above, 47 or 50% of the student identify performing the work in the public another medium of copyright violation. This was approved by 10 or 76.9% of the staff. Making

adaptation of the work is also included in the list. 43 or 45.7% of the student attest to that 9 or 69.2% of the staff also confirmed that.

Lastly 44 or 46.8% of the students' belief that broadcasting the work over an electronic media is another contributor to copyright abuses. This was also approved by 8 or 61.5% of the staff of both institutions.

Respondents were told to identify suitable measure to be taken to arrest

Copyright abuses.

Table 4.10: Measures to Curtail Copyright Abuses

Answer	FREQUENCY					
	Students			Staff		
	Agree %	Disagree %	No idea %	Agree %	Disagree %	No idea %
Educate the general public about copyright	79 84.0	2 2.1	13 13.8	13 100	0 0	0 0
Copyright should be taught in secondary and tertiary institution	64 68.1	15 16.0	15 16.0	13 100	0 0	0 0
Copyright tribunal should be established	60 63.8	21 23.3	26 27.7	13 100	0 0	0 0
Higher penalties should be imposed to copyright offenders	53 56.4	24 25.5	17 18.0	11 84.6	2 15.4	0 0
Special anti-piracy squad should be trained to combat piracy	66 70.2	11 11.7	17 18.0	13 100	0 0	0 0
Licenses should be given to publisher to encourage local production of scarce information materials	69 73.4	11 11.7	14 14.9	13 100	0 0	0 0

As we can see from the table above 79 or 84% of the student agreed that educating the public is a step in the right direction in curtailing copyright abuses. This was also supported by 13 or 100% of the staff.

Introducing copyright into the curriculum of secondary and tertiary institution is a good idea according to 64 or 68.1% of the student. 13 or 100% of the staff also reaffirmed that.

Establishment of copyright tribunal should be welcome according to 60 or 63.8% of the student. 13 or 100% of the staff also approved that.

Higher penalties should be imposed to copyright case according to 53 or 56.5% of the student. 11 or 84.6% of the staff also agreed on that.

Special anti-piracy squad should be trained to combat piracy according to 66 or 70.2% of the student, 13 or 100% of the staff also approved that.

Issuing license to local publisher can also help according to 69 or 73.4% of the student, 13 or 100% of the staff are fully in support of that too.

Respondents were asked to suggest other role that they feel the government can play to combat copyright violation.

Table 4.11: Role of Government in Combating Copyright Abuses in the Country

Answer	FREQUENCY					
	Students			Staff		
	Agree %	Disagree %	No idea %	Agree %	Disagree %	No idea %
Government should provide stake-holder with incentive	66 70.2	9 9.6	19 20.2	10 76.9	2 15.4	1 7.7
Government should established strong copyright enforcement mechanism	75 79.8	5 5.3	14 14.9	13 100	0	0 0
Government should be the fore-runner in educating the public	79 84.0	9 9.6	6 6.4	13 100	0 0	0 0

The table above reveals that government should provide incentive to stake-holder in copyright business according to 66 or 70.2% of the students and 10 or 76.9% of the staff also hold on to that too.

Government should established strong copyright enforcement mechanisms is another suggestion given by 75 or 79.8% of the students, 13 or 100% of the staff supported that too.

Government should be fore-runner in educating the public is another suggestion given by 79 or 84% of the student, 13 or 100% of the staff also approved it.

4.2 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The data collected from the designed closed ended questionnaires which were administered to staff and students of F.U.T Minna and Niger State C.O.E Minna as analyzed and presented in a simple tabulation and percentages previously revealed the following results.

Table 4.3 tells us that 84 or 89.4% of the student and 13 or 100% of the staff of both Institutions are fully aware of the existence of copyright law. On the contrary, table 4.5 and 4.6 as certain that, though the students were informed about copyright law, yet some are ignorant of their negative actions on the intellectual properties

Table 4.6 reveals that most students violate the law not because they wanted to do so. Some decide to violate the law due to lack of knowledge about the concept of copyright. Other violated the law because of the scarcity of some information materials in the market. However, it could be observed in table 6 that 38 or 40.4% of the students and 5 or 38.5% of the staff saw copyright violation as good business. 19 Or 20.2% of the students derived pleasure from the act.

Factor that catalyzes copyright abuse can be seen in table 4.6 and 4.7. 41 or 43% of the students admitted that they lack of knowledge about the concept of copyright while 0 or 0% of the staff confirmed that they are well informed about copyright. Reason for these could be attributed to the nature of their job (staff) and some of the students are just joining the school system.

68 or 72.3% of the students and 8 or 61.6% of the staff in table 4.7 declare that availability of printing materials like paper, cassettes, CDs e.t.c also encourage copyright violation. Few of them have no idea, others disagree. This implies that some of them are not aware of the information revolution going on in the country.

47 or 50.0% of the students and 10 or 76.9% of the staff believe that lack of strong copyright system is a contributing factor. The staff responses prove that they are more current than the students.

66 or 70.2% of the students and 13 or 100% of the staff attested that cost of reproducing a copyrighted work is cheaper than the cost of origination. The staff responds show that they know more about what it takes to produce a product of the mind.

From table 4.9, it can be seen that out of the listed entries, photocopying and piracy have the highest response. 85 or 90.4% of the students and 12 or 93.3% of staff believe that photocopying and piracy are the major medium of copyright violation. This implies that most of populations are participating in the act.

Table 4.10 spelt out the suitable measures to curtail copyright violation. From the table, it can be seen that 79 or 84.0% of the students and 13 or 100% of the staff believe that educating the general public should be paramount in curtailing the menace. This implies that some people need to be informed about the subject matter.

Issuing licenses to the local publishers can foster constant supply of scarce information resources was endorsed by 69 or 73.4% of the students and 13 or 100% of the staff.. the response for the staff also tells us that they are more knowledgeable about the happening than the students.

Special anti-piracy squad should be trained to combat piracy. This was also endorsed by 66 or 70.2% of the students and 13 or 100% of the staff. Reason for this could be attributed to the fact that the law enforcement agency are not measuring up to the mandate given to them and hence there is need for a new squad.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.0 INTRODUCTION

The chapter contains information that provides a comprehensive, analytical and logical conclusion of the research base on the previous chapters.

5.1 SUMMARY

Base on the information obtained from the previous chapters. It is glaring that majority of Nigerian student knows about copyright law. The draw back here is some of them are ignorant of the negative practice which is capable of depriving authors from their economic benefits. The major and the commonest harmful practice often perpetrated by students are photocopying and piracy.

The essence of copyright law like I said initially is not to restrict potential user of information access to such resources, rather it was designed to strike a balance between the just reward given to author and user accessibility to information. However this is provided in the doctrine of fair use. Fair use is the act of reproducing few pages from a copyrighted work without preventing the author from his economic gain.

It was observed that most students violate the laws not because they wanted to do so rather, they tend to violate the law because they lack knowledge about the safety or fair use of copyright. More so, some of them violate the law because they have no choice. Most important information resources can hardly be source for in the market due to scarcity.

Beside the above mentioned reason, lack of strong copyright system, advancement in technology and cost of reproduction is cheaper than cost of origination are other facilitator of copyright abuses.

Copyright abuses are one of the greatest parasites eating deep into the fabric of Nigeria economy.

Photocopying and piracy are the major ways copyright are violated among Nigeria students.

Educating the general public about copyright, creating a conducive environment for stakeholders in copyright business, implementation (in full) and enforcement of strong system is the way out to the menace of copyright abuses in the country. It is a collective responsibility.

5.2 CONCLUSION

It is crystal clear to note that an average Nigerian student is aware of the existence of copyright law. No doubt the growth and development of any nation is a function of the quality and the quantity of information created and disseminated by the tireless effort of the inhabitant of that country.

“Knowledge is power”. These are created by people with creative mind who need our protection, support and encouragement from the government, private organization and the general public at large.

Therefore, for Nigeria as a nation to be able to achieve the millennium development goal, a strong copyright mechanism needs to be in place. That is the step in the right direction.

5.3 RECOMMENDATIONS

This research has captured one area that was neglected by the Nigerian government. Copyright abuses supposed to be conspicuous, but this is not so in Nigerian situation. There is no doubt that this research is capable of changing the mindset of not only the government but the society at large. It capture the root causes of copyright abuses, its negative effect, some possible ways this law is abused and suitable measures to be taken to curtail those evil practice.

I, respectfully and humbly wish to recommend that the government and the general public should strictly adhere to the following recommendations. This will help in eradicating copyright theft and also act as a catalyst in achieving the millennium development goal.

1. Government should provide copyright stake-holder with incentive to boost their activities
2. Educating the general public about the concept of copyright through public enlightenment programmes such as seminar, workshop, electronic media and mass media. The people in the rural or remote area should also be considered because they are part of the problem.
3. Intellectual property law should be incorporated into the curricular of secondary and tertiary institutions in the country. Students need to be taught about the positive usage of copyright.
4. Licensing option should be created for local publisher. This will eradicate the rate of copyright abuses cause by scarcity of some information resources.
5. Strong copyright system discourages investment in copyright theft. Therefore, the law enforcement agencies should impound, destroy or even sell equipments used by copyright law offenders.
6. Copyright tribunal in charge with the responsibility of passing judgment over copyright cases should be established.

7. Higher penalties on different copyright abuses should be enforced.
8. Training of special anti-piracy squad to combat piracy should be welcome.
9. Government should be the fore-runner in educating the general public about copyright law.
10. Copyright council should create a network of collection societies to administer the collection and distribution of royalties to the respective author.

REFERENCES

Ali, S. I (1987, Saturday June 6). Book piracy. New Nigeria p12

APA referencing ([http. // start up. Curtin edu au / Library / apa. html](http://start.up.Curtin.edu.au/Library/apa.html))

October 21, 2003 p1 – 9.

Apotiade, J. K (2004). Relationship between textbook development and copyright law. In E. C madu (ed) Technology for information management and service: Modern Library and information centres in developing countries p 177 – 187.

Ekeh, F. I (2003) Research methodology and statistic in education Abakaliki mado press Ltd.

Federal University of Technology Minna 2007 student hand book. Minna Olalekan press. P2

Flint, M. F (1997). A user Guide to copyright (4th ed) London Dublin: Butter worths.

Gurnsey, J (1995). Copyright theft. Aldershot England: Aslib Gower house.

Higo, A (1989). The publishing chain from conception to consumer. In the publisher – magazine of the Nigerian Publisher Association vol. 1, No. 2 March 1989, p1

Ike, C (1992). The scope and the implication of the Nigerian copyright decrees. In copyright news.

Kent, A (1972) Copyright. In Encyclopedia of library and information science
(Vol. 6 p 33 – 75).

Harrod's Librarians' Glossary and Reference Book (1990) 7th ed. In prytherch , R. Aldershot
England: Gower publishing Company Limited.

Krejcie, R. V and Morgan, D. W (1970). Determining sample size for research activities;
Educational and psychological measurement p 608 – 610

Ojiji, C.O (1991) Book Piracy in Nigeria – lagos: the world intellectual property organization/the
Nigeria copyright council 21-23 may 1991. p22

Oxford Advanced Learners Dictionary (2000) in Wehmeier, S and Ashby, M (Eds). Oxford: Oxford University Press.

Rosenberg, V (1990) Copyright and the new technology, in on-line information 90. 4th international online information meeting proceedings, London 11 – 13 December 1990, Oxford: Learned information 1990.

Rothenberg, S (1983) Copyright. In Encyclopedia Americana (Vol. 7 p772 - 776).

The laws of the federation of Nigeria (1990, Vol. 5 chapter 68 - 87).

Veliotes, N (1988) letter from Nicolas Veliotes, president of AAP. To Harvey winter, director of the US Department of state, office of business practices. Quoted in penick, P.H copyright and scowling publisher / library interface; serial librarian, 15 [3 + 4], 1988, p55 – 62.

Wall, R. A (1993). Copyright made easier London: Alib the Association for information management house.

Unpublished document

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2006 Lit 415 (intellectual property law) lecture note

APPENDIX

DEPARTMENT OF LIBRARY AND INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY, FEDERAL UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY, MINNA

Dear Respondent,

I am a final year student of the above named department conducting a research on the topic:
**“Copyright abuses in Nigerian higher institution: causes and effects; on intellectual properties:
Case study of Federal University of Technology Minna and Niger State College of Education
Minna”.**

Overleaf is a questionnaire designed to enable me collect relevant data for my research study.
I shall be grateful and delighted if you could read the content of the questionnaire, properly tick as
indicated and fill in your responses appropriately where necessary.

All responses shall be treated confidentially and use only for the purpose of the research study.

Thanks in anticipation for your cooperation and your understanding.

Yours faithfully,

Makoshi Stephen Mikah

I humbly wish to solicit for your support by providing me with the following information. This will enable me to be able to accomplish the research I am working on. Thanks for supporting my education on this regard.

QUESTIONNAIRE

SECTION A (RESPONDENT'S PERSONAL DATA)

- i. What is your occupation?
 - a. Student []
 - b. Civil Servant []
- ii. Tick your age group
 - a. 16 – 20yrs []
 - b. 21 – 25yrs []
 - c. 26 – 30yrs []
 - d. 31 – 35yrs []
 - e. 36yrs and above []

SECTION B

1. Have you heard of copyright law before?
 - a. Yes []
 - b. No []
 - c. Not sure []
2. What do you do whenever you discover there is a copy of an information material you can hardly find in the market?

[**Note:** Excluding option c, you can tick more than one option]

 - a. I always photocopy the whole pages of the book to have my own personal copy []

- b. I use to duplicate any video, musicals or even software for my personal use []
- c. Undecided []

3. Do you know that your action towards such material is copyright violation?

- a. Yes []
- b. No []
- c. Not sure []

In the table below, tick the option that accurately answer the following question

4. Why do you choose to violate copyright law?

	Agree	Disagree	No Idea
i. Because I lack knowledge about copyright law.			
ii. Because some of the important information materials are not available in the market due to scarcity.			
iii. It is a good business to make money within the shortest range of time.			
iv. It is fun to violate copyright law.			

5. What other factor do you think might be responsible for copyright abuses?

	Agree	Disagree	No Idea
i. Availability of printing material, such as paper, empty cassette and CD – Rom for reproduction.			
ii. Availability of Hi –tech equipment for printing and mass production/dissemination of the information material.			
iii. Lack of strong copyright system.			
iv. Cost of reproducing an original information material is cheaper than the cost of producing a new original material.			

6. Do you believe that copyright law violation has an adverse effect on Nigeria economy and intellectual property development?

a. Agree [] b. Disagree [] c. No Idea []

7. The following are ways through which copyright law is violated.

	Agree	Disagree	No Idea
i. Photocopying and piracy			
ii. Issuing the copies of the work to the public for commercial purpose.			
iii. Renting or lending copies of the work to the public for business purpose.			
iv. Performing, showing or playing the work in public.			
v. Making an adaptation of the work			
vi. Broadcasting the work over electronic media or cable programme service			

8. The following are suitable measures to be taken to arrest copyright law violation

	Agree	Disagree	No Idea
i. Educating the general public on copyright awareness.			
ii. Copyright should be taught in both secondary and tertiary institutions.			
iii. Copyright tribunal which is charged with the responsibility of passing judgment over all copyright cases should be established.			
iv. Higher penalties against different copyright abuses and the sell of the equipment used by offenders should be strongly enforced.			
v. Training of special anti – piracy squad to combat piracy should also be instituted.			
vi. License should be given to publisher and distributors to allow them to produce locally the scarce information material.			

9. What other role do you feel the government should play in the fight against copyright law violation?

	Agree	Disagree	No Idea
i. Government should provide authors and other stake – holder in the copyright business with incentive to boost their activities.			
ii. Government should establish a strong copyright enforcement mechanism to discourage investment in piracy.			
iii. Government should be the fore – runner in educating the general public about copyright law by organizing seminars, conferences and workshops for the general public.			